

DIGITAL ECONOMY – A DEMAND OF THE TIME

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Annotatsiya:

Ushbu maqolada globallashuv jarayonining zamonaviy iqtisodiy munosabatlarga ko'rsatgan ta'siri hamda raqamli iqtisodiyotning jahon xo'jaligidagi o'rni tahlil qilingan. Maqolada raqamli transformatsiyaning afzalliklari bilan bir qatorda, kiberxavfsizlik, raqamli tafovut va ma'lumotlar xavfsizligi kabi dolzarb muammolar ham tahlil etilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari globallashuv sharoitida raqamli iqtisodiyotning strategik ahamiyatga ega ekanini ko'rsatadi.

Annotation:

This article analyzes the impact of the globalization process on modern economic relations and the role of the digital economy in the world economy. Along with the advantages of digital transformation, the article also analyzes such pressing problems as cybersecurity, digital divide, and data security. The results of the study show that the digital economy is of strategic importance in the context of globalization.

Аннотация:

В данной статье анализируется влияние глобализации на современные экономические отношения и роль цифровой экономики в мировой экономике. Наряду с преимуществами цифровой трансформации, в статье также анализируются актуальные проблемы, такие как кибербезопасность, цифровое неравенство и безопасность данных. Результаты исследования показывают, что цифровая экономика имеет стратегическое значение в контексте глобализации.

Keywords: Globalization process, information, technologies, M.A. Nikitenkova, economics, Digital economy, artificial intelligence, K. Schwab.

Introduction. Today, the globalization process is deeply penetrating all sectors of the world economy. As a result of the speed of information exchange, the expansion of economic cooperation between countries, increased competition in international markets, and the rapid development of innovative technologies, the content of the global economic system is fundamentally changing. In particular, the popularization of digital technologies, as one of the main features of the XXIst century, the widespread use of the Internet, the introduction of technologies such as artificial intelligence, cloud platforms, electronic payment systems, and big data (Big Data) into everyday life, have laid the foundation for

the formation of the digital economy. Therefore, the digital economy is emerging as an integral part of the globalization process.

The digital revolution has changed our lives and societies to an unprecedented extent, creating both enormous opportunities and some challenges in 25 years. The development of the digital economy is one of the priorities for leading countries such as the USA, Great Britain, Germany, and Japan [2. – P. 309.].

The digital economy is a new system that implements political, economic, scientific, social, cultural, and educational relations using digital technologies, and the sustainable development of the service sector in the digital economy is of particular importance. The digital economy involves the digitization of all business processes related to the creation, promotion, and sale of goods and services. Digital information has become the main factor of production, the main asset of companies, and plays a key role in all economic activities. “The information environment of the service business, which provides access to information about the activities of economic systems in real time in a global network, is of particular importance. Digital infrastructure includes a set of technologies that provide computing, telecommunications, and networking needs of companies operating on a digital basis” [1. – P. 1472.].

Literature review and methodology

Many researchers approach the digital economy from different perspectives. For example, M.A. Nikitenkova defines the information economy as a stage in the development of productive forces [3. – P. 310]. M. Porat is considered the first scientist to use the term information economy [4. P. 1472]. K. Schwab highlights the beginning of the fourth industrial revolution and its main features.

Results and discussion

The main features of the digital economy are:

- The dominance of information resources: information and data play a central role in creating economic value;
- Digital infrastructure: the Internet, cloud computing, mobile communications and other digital technologies are widely used in all aspects of the economy;
- New business models: e-commerce, online services, platform economy and other innovative forms are developing;
- Global connectivity: economic processes are interconnected through information networks around the world;

– Intellectual capital and creativity: knowledge, innovation, and creative ideas become the main factors of economic growth [1. – B.1473].

The following advantages of the digital economy are distinguished [6]:

- it is estimated to increase labor productivity by up to 40%;
- the digital economy has the ability to collect, use and analyze huge amounts of machine-readable data (digital data);
- the emergence of new forms of work sold through online platforms;
- digital transformation is a change in the trade infrastructure for specialized services;
- exports of industrial products are now increasingly dependent on ICT products and services;
- the digital economy has generated enormous wealth in a very short time, but this wealth is concentrated around a small number of individuals, companies and countries. Under current policies and regulations, this trajectory can continue, but it will lead to increased inequality.

At the same time, there are some contradictory aspects of this economy. They are:

- new technologies, especially artificial intelligence, will inevitably lead to major changes in the labor market, including job losses in some sectors and large-scale creation of opportunities in others;
- the digital economy requires a new and diverse set of skills, a new generation of social protection policies, and new relationships between work and leisure;
- the digital economy also poses new risks, from cybersecurity breaches to facilitation of illicit economic activity and the intrusion of privacy [2. – P. 310].

There is a close and interdependent relationship between the global information space and the digital economy. The global information space serves as a platform for the digital economy, as it ensures the flow of information and services around the world. At the same time, the digital economy stimulates the development of the global information space, further expanding information exchange through new technologies, platforms and business models [3. – P. 310].

The global information space is a complex interconnected system of information flows, digital infrastructures, users and information systems, which allows for the exchange of information regardless of national borders. In such an environment, new economic sectors such as the digital economy, information economy, network economy and creative economy are taking shape and developing in close interdependence.

The global information space consists of the following main components: information resources containing information, data and knowledge recorded on appropriate carriers; organizational structures that ensure the collection, processing, storage, distribution, retrieval and transmission of information; means of communication (usually the Internet) that provide individuals and organizations with access to information resources. The development of information and communication technologies and the concepts of the digital economy play an important role in the global economy today [3. P. 309.].

Conclusion

In conclusion, our state is successfully fulfilling its role in creating the necessary conditions for the development of the digital economy in our country, which is evidenced by the achieved results and ambitious goals set for the near future.

Through the digitization of the service sector, changes can be achieved in the labor market. The structure of the labor market in the service sector is also changing, the disappearance of some professions and the emergence of new modern professions are predicted. Working in the digital service economy requires new cognitive, social behavior and digital skills, which must be formed in the process of training personnel capable of working in the digital economy.

References

1. Nasrullayev Nurbek. Global Information Space and Concepts of the Digital Economy. // Scientific Electronic Journal "Digital Economy". 2020.
2. Ilyasov Asrorjon. The Current State of the Digital Economy: Problems and Solutions. // Scientific electronic journal "Economics and innovative technologies". 2021, No. 1.
3. Machlup F. The Production and Distribution of Knowledge in the United States. – Princeton, 1962.
4. Bell D. The Coming of Post-Industrial Society. – New York, 1973.
5. Akram Odilovich. "Ways of developing the service sector in the digital economy". // Scientific electronic journal "XXI century: science and education issues". 2024, No. 2.
6. <https://tiu-edu.uz/media/books/2024/05/25/1715405480.pdf>

